

Audience Onboarding and Offboarding for Emotional VR Storytelling

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ABSTRACT

Most immersive VR/XR experiences in public spaces and online, expect that audiences need only to put on a headset and start their excellent experience. However, it is now evident that many audiences are still unfamiliar with VR/XR. And even when they have tried VR, they still require experience guiding on how to move and interact within the experience, often called "onboarding" as well as "offboarding" to help them reintegrate back to reality, especially if the content of the experience is extremely emotional and affecting.

Many VR/XR artists and designers are now becoming aware of their responsibility to create a better "onboarding" audience experience for their immersive journeys, develop more accessible interactions with the medium, providing effective methods of guiding visitors from the real to the virtual and back (offboarding).

This talk provides insights from her own VR/haptic installation artworks *INTER/her* and *Mammary Mountain* over the last few years in working with audiences and how to care for first time VR audience members when encountering XR works.

CCS CONCEPTS

- Human-centered computing
 - ~ Interaction design
 - ~ Interaction design process and methods
 - ~ User centered design

KEYWORDS

VR/XR Guiding/ Invigilation, Onboarding / Offboarding. Managing narrative emotional content, Supporting audiences of VR/XR, Health-based VR storytelling

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1 Context

Over the last three years, I have been touring around the UK and Canada with the artwork *INTER/her An intimate journey inside the female body*, a Virtual Reality installation experience, which includes a haptic garment – with vibration motors in it – placed around the lower abdomen to stimulate and connect visitors to their bodies in tandem with the stories of reproductive diseases that take place inside in those areas. It is experienced inside a tent that visitors crawl into, like womb space to amplify the content of the work.

One of the great learnings from exhibiting this work has been from the responses from and impact on the audiences who have come to see it, primarily because it has a very emotional narrative around the experiences that women have faced dealing with reproductive health illnesses and ailments and the poor diagnosis and treatment that they have encountered within the healthcare system. It has been so amazing to observe how different people respond to it, and especially women have seemed very validated by the stories from real women, while men have come out shocked and with great amount of empathy due to not realising what their partners, daughters, sisters and mothers have gone through. It has been a very enlightening process these 3 years.

More recently I have worked in collaboration with two other artists Tara Baoth Mooney and Mafj Alvarez, in making a new similar VR/ Haptic work called *Mammary Mountain*, exhibited in 3 locations since it was completed in November 2023 and at the time of writing. *Mammary Mountain* is a similar but different work about the breast cancer treatment journey and contains stories from 8 different and mostly women have experiences, of all the different main treatments that a patient can go through once they have been diagnosed with breast cancer, from surgery, to mastectomy, to chemotherapy, to radiotherapy and hormone therapy.

2 Staging and setting

One of the main criteria to enable a meaningful experience for audience members for both artworks, is to ensure that the technology is understood by or simple the visitor, either by showing them how to use the headset and controller and/or helping them to put it on. In both projects, this "onboarding" has been critical to the visitors to having a good experience and has been done primarily through excellent 1st person, relatable stories, and well-planned interaction design, but also partially through props and spatial considerations within in the real-world installation of bringing them into the experience.

Figure 1: Visitor with 'haptic corset' inside the 'sitting womb' for the audience testing for *INTER/her* ©May 30th, 2021, Camille Baker.

In addition, the haptic vibration garment not only connects the body to the narrative storytelling, but the ritual of dressing visitors and making them feel safe in the space, sometimes adding a nice sent to the space helps them comfortable, even though the content of the narrative journey in the virtual world can be disturbing, sad and triggering. This sense of nurturing and care has been equally important to the content. Then the assistance of visitors out of the experience back into reality is also carefully planned and essential to the success of the impact of the work. By making sure that the technology is taken away by myself, a colleague and / or volunteer and then sitting with visitor to see and ask how they feel after and about the experience, is critical to providing a lasting impression, especially since so many of our visitors for both projects are older women who have never done VR before. In additional for *Mammary Mountain*, we make sure that visitors are taken out of the garment and seated in a place that's comfortable and enables them to reflect on the experience and then that they have a moment to discuss what they experienced. Pre- and post- experience caretaking are considered "on and off boarding" for both projects, and are a critical part of the experience for us as artists.

Figure 2: visitors in the breast chairs for *Mammary Mountain*, Paisley, Scotland ©April 27th, 2024, Camille Baker (in collaboration with Tara Baath Mooney and Maf'j Alvarez)

These terms have been adopted by the VR/ XR "industry", but as artists we prefer to called it "guiding" and "debriefing" the ritual and/ or performance of it seems to be the main difference between an fully absorbing and "immersive" work and a museum work where there is often no guidance and an assumption that a) only

young people familiar with VR or gaming will try it and b) they will know what to do, which cannot be assumed.

3 Onboarding and Offboarding

Taking insights from Laryssa Whittaker in her article *Onboarding and Offboarding in virtual reality: a user-centered framework for audience experience across genres and spaces*, who has done thorough research on "on and off boarding" in recent years and looked at immersive theatre, games and older conceptual constructs of the transition between the real and the virtual in other earlier virtual worlds to find the common elements that make the experience immersive. She focusses on five aspects for onboarding and offboarding for immersive audiences, which are platform, place, genre, time and users and how they need to be designed to the optimal experience.

Figure 3: A framework for onboarding and offboarding immersive audiences ©2023 L Whittaker The framework is adapted from the StoryFutures Audience Toolkit (Bennett et al. 2021),

Whittaker's framework was a happy find, which we inadvertently implemented with *INTER/her* and *Mammary Mountain* without having ever seen this framework before writing this paper. So, to put these works through the framework we developed the work as below:

In terms of *platform* for *INTER/her* we used the Oculus Quest 2 because it was wireless and easy to work with and we were able to connect the Oculus to the haptic easily. Equally with *Mammary Mountain*, we chose to use the PICO 4 for because it wasn't in the Meta universe, so didn't connect users in the same way, and it was better in terms of its resolution and pass through feature, and again still a portable platform, as well as being easy to work with. We initially were going to use passthrough, but we decided in the end to make the work completely 360 animation without stops and starts with passthrough, because it worked with the metaphor of getting on a "treatment train" and being unable to get off in terms of cancer.

For the controls, we tried to keep it minimal in both projects, but without any *Mammary Mountain* to keep it completely accessible, but in both cases, we have the haptic dimension that adds the embodied element. The haptic element also involved the ritual of dressing the visitor as part of the on boarding and to get them into the mode of being in this new experience, and then the undressing

at the end to help them to transition out of the experience from both the virtual and physical perspective.

For *place*, both had a bespoke physical installations to bring visitors from the physical to the virtual: for *INTER/her* which is a tent-based experience, with a crawl in space for sitting on beanbag chair, in a cosy and closed environment. For *Mammary Mountain*, we made bespoke 360 chairs for the “treatment” and created a clinic waiting room environment, room hospital props and uniforms, so that it created that sense of connection between the real world and the virtual world, in terms of the visitors entering the cancer context.

In terms of the *genre*, the choice was made to use animation in both cases, because it was able to create this abstract world that still puts you into the frame of the content, but also makes it not too realistic, since we include real voices to connect you to the difficult stories and the experiences.

For the *time* context of Whittaker’s framework, *INTER/her* was 16 minutes and has distinct stories and each only around 1-2 minutes and keeps you moving on a track to keep people engaged and focussed and not bored. However, with *Mammary Mountain*, we had several different treatments for the medical cancer treatment experience that we wanted to explore, from diagnosis, to surgery, to mastectomy, to chemotherapy, and then radiotherapy, then a reprieve, followed by hormone therapy, and a life after treatment scenes. We had a very clear narrative arc with the stories that we wanted to cover and through different people’s voices and experiences.

When considering *users*, we found that we attracted mostly older women because of the topics, not because of the platform and most of them have had a little or no VR experience. For *INTER/her* there was a slightly broader visitor base, with men and women people of different ages and abilities, but again majority you have never used VR and came because of the topic.

For the frame of the work, it has really been about the body, going into the body, and focus on healthcare and the hidden and experiences that primarily women face in both pieces, and which are not always expressed or known about in the general public.

More will be discussed on *INTER/her* and *Mammary Mountain* within the context of onboarding and offboarding during the presentation.

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